

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

THE IMPACT OF MOTIVATION ON LEARNING

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Abstract

Goal setting is the building distinct and feasible targets or objectives for learning and has become an essential way on learners' motivation. The major functions of it are enhancing task interests, reducing boredom and promoting goal clarity. Learners need to consider and know what to obtain out of the educational process. That is why the learning orientation is closely associated with a motivational one by being concentrative on understanding, acquiring knowledge and developing one's competence and ability. This goal value learning should to incorporate the standards of achievements. Goal setting in learning is commonly regarded as one of the strategies that also encourages learner autonomy, which is a long-term purpose of education and a basic factor in successful learning.

Keywords: learner's motivation, goal setting, learning process, decision making, language learning, teaching strategies.

Introduction. The more explicit goals learners have, the higher outcomes they will get. Teachers should make powerful effects on learners' intentions for learning and academic engagement. That is why learners understanding of classroom instructions is largely related to motivational beliefs and behaviors that learners embrace. Goals are assumed to be cognitive representations or knowledge structures, which are sensitive to both contextual, internal personal factors. Accordingly, strong classroom contexts or experimental manipulations where the context defines the situation and appropriate behavior in many ways, can influence individuals to activate different goals than the autonomy support can be distinguished on the basis of indefinite various features such as suggesting options, interpretation of relevance, and opportunities for learners to express perspectives with regard to the efficacy of the learning tasks. Autonomy includes encourage creative and imaginative ideas, encourage questions and other contributions from learners, share as much responsibility for organizing the learning process with the students as possible.

Learners who value distant future plans, particularly, self-set future goals, and those who comprehend positive relations between current school tasks and future goals, improve a grown interest in their schoolwork. This increased interest enhances effective learning in the school environment. Future goals are substantial for learners' encouragement toward the learning process. The adaptive effect of internally organizing future goals offers a plausible means of developing learners' educational performance. Future goals should get attention in multi-ethnic classrooms by inspiring learners to figure out their future and set their peculiar goals. (Andriessen I., Phaet K., Lens W. Future Goal-setting. Task Motivation and learning of Minority and Nonminority Students in Dutch Schools, *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 2006,

pp.827-850). Learners interest include selecting interesting tasks and topics, offering a variety of materials and activities, making tasks challenging to involve the learners, and using learners' interests rather than tests or grades, to encourage learning.

Through explanation, discourse, and elaboration learners help each other's learning. The teacher facilitates this process by arranging time and face-to-face seating to promote interaction. Learners not only account for facts and concepts but they are also engaged in discussion, visually and aurally. This prepares learners to an intercultural knowledge environment and is grounded on verbal communication. In such environment learners knowledge and skills can be achieved, and their discourse embodies learners' initiative rather than just answering teacher's questions. Motivating learning-to-learn skills is feasible when learners are listening to one another rather than just to their instructor. The main role of this method is that all learners have an equal opportunity to express their valuable and constructive ideas to contribute to their task. Effective skills such as conflict resolution, decision-making processes, effective leadership, and active listening should be taught learners who do not already process them. Learners as a group discuss and evaluate their learning goals how well they do it by working collaboratively. Teachers cannot teach social competences to their learners directly, since learners themselves need to cooperate more in classroom discussion, as today's classrooms are based on much more learner-initiated intellectual behavior and constructive talk. Both Day and Bryce revealed that by utilizing cooperative learning teachers should espouse participation but avoid closed-ended questions, autocratic and recitative styles in classroom discourses. (Day S.P., and Bryce T.G. Does the Discussion of Socio Scientific Issues require a Par-

adigm Shift in Science Teachers' Thinking? *International Journal of Science Education*, 2011, pp. 156-175).

The effectiveness of cooperative learning mainly focuses on student-to-student and student-to-teacher not teacher-to-student approach. (Asakawa M., Kanamaru A., and Plaza T. *Useful expressions for Implementing Cooperative Learning in English*, *The electronic Journal for English as a Second Language*, 2016, p.196). For living in a time of unprecedented technological change, technology-enhanced learning is a thought-provoking approach to the learning process for effectively cultivating learner's digital competences by promoting more learner-centered teaching approaches. Information Communication technology has been improving considerably and impacting on teaching activities and develops meaningful assessments and inspires learners to study with their full potential.

Classroom visualizations may also enrich learning by strengthening learners' motivation and attention. Technology in education enables learners to convey, visualize their understandings, research, arrange resources, make notes, and control cognitive loads. That is why animation and sound effects grow learners' interests since learning without software can be dull and lifeless. Nevertheless learning with software enhances a great impact on learners' learning and this way helps them to visualize and make an enjoyable learning process. Motivation is an immensely indispensable foundation for learners' academic development. The state of lacking an intention to learn is an inevitable fact on education. If learners are academically motivated, they will comprehend school and learning as valuable. In this case learners, teachers and education are leading variables. The best way to increase student motivation is to follow modern trends such as helping to set definite goals for learners, give them autonomy, improve their digital skills, providing flipped classroom learning, create problem based environment where learners associate the initial knowledge with the current one and learn from each other.

The suggested ways increase academic performance and achievement of learners. (Mary Spratt, Alan Pulverness, Melanie Williams. *The teaching knowledge test course*. Cambridge University Press, 2011, 255p).

Flipped learning is a pedagogical approach in which learners are provided with short videos for watching at home, but in classroom they are mainly focused on exercises, discourses to create an interactive learning medium. The flipped classroom methods promotes learners' engagement in learning through application and practice. This method is composed of three fundamental pillars such as online videos, physical classes and an interactive platform. The key aim of the flipped classroom is to form active learning and involve learners concentrating on conceptual knowledge rather than factual recall. (Mason G.S., Shuman T.R., and Cook K.E. *Comparing the effectiveness of an inverted classroom to a traditional classroom in an upper-division engineering course*, *IEEE transaction on Education*, 2013, pp. 430-435). More flexible learning arrangements can be offered to students by the flipped

settings. (Zhai X., Gu J., Liu H. *An experimental learning perspective on students' satisfaction model in a flipped classroom context*. *Journal of educational technology and society*, 2017, pp.198-210).

Digital story telling is a new practice form where learner use digital tools to narrate their delightful stories. It must be noted that digital storytelling develop learners' motivation and engagement in story development projects. Digital storytelling increases productivity in classroom learning environment and also students' learning experiences with the help of open ended and creative devices. Computer, digital camera, internet and photo storage can be the indication of best motivating productive tools on students' encouragement. Furthermore, its objectives are higher order thinking and motivation transversal skills.

Combination of these students' centered learning strategies is facilitated by digital storytelling. Student, engagement, reflection for deep learning, project based learning and effective integration of technology into instruction are related to these strategies. (Sadik A. *Digital storytelling*, *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 2008, pp.487-506). There are a great deal of using digital storytelling in education. They are: to provide new version instead of traditional ones, to personify learning experience, to make interpretation and the using of certain themes, to form real life situation in a simple and inexpensive way, to make better engagement of students' in the learning process. A qualitative research helps to determine the problem and improves an approach to the problem. It will be advantages to comprehend the crux of the problem. The goal of the research paper is to present the importance of motivation for learners and show the ways how to implement reasonable methods, which in turns, affect learners' academic achievement and center on strengthening learners' motivation and engagement. Lack of motivation or the passion for learning is due to a number of students attend physically in the classroom but mentally absent, which is the indicator of not concentrating themselves on the experience of learning.

This research is carried out considering phenomenological approach, since the inquirer collects data from persons who have experienced the phenomenon and develops a composite description of the essence of the experience for all of the individuals. (Creswell J.W. *Educational research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*, Sydney, 2012, p.243). It emphasizes on the necessity of personal experiences and its interpretation. Data collection from phenomenological researches is composed of in-depth interviews and multiple interviews with participants. Accordingly, teachers will be interviewed to get information about learners' motivation. In this regard, signing a consent letter in advance will be helpful. Theory or concept sampling will be used in this study to know teachers and students' perspectives towards the topic. Having carried out manifold investigations on learner motivation, it becomes obvious that innovative methods improve the effectiveness of instruction in the school setting and nurture learners' ambition to study, collaborate and tackle problems.

Conclusion.

Goal-setting, cooperative, problem-based and technology enhanced learning keeps learners engaged, creates a sense of willingness on learners stay focused, and gives an opportunity to learners to interact. All these ways provide in-depth learning, a stronger pillar of the community as well as ownership and enforce learners to put their maximum endeavor in learning. The suggested ways support learners' learning by inspiring them to express and share their ideas and knowledge in a worthwhile way. The approaches make learner think, find solutions to the given problem and fully focus on the results of activities.

References

1. Mary Spratt, Alan Pulverness, Melanie Williams. The teaching knowledge test course. Cambridge University Press, 2011, 255p.
2. Assor A., Kaplan H., and Roth G. Autonomy enhancing and suppressing teacher behaviors predicting students' engagement and school work. *British Journal of Education Psychology*, 2002, pp. 261-278.
3. Andriessen I., Phalet K., Lens W. Future Goal-setting. Task Motivation and learning of Minority and Nonminority Students in Dutch Schools, *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 2006, pp.827-850. *Filologiya məsələləri*, № 4, 2021 – 18
4. Day S.P., and Bryce T.G. Does the Discussion of Socio Scientific Issues require a Paradigm Shift in Science Teachers' Thinking?, *International Journal of Science Education*, 2011, p.175.
5. Asakawa M., Kanamaru A., and Plaza T. Useful expressions for Implementing Cooperative Learning in English, *The electronic Journal for English as a Second Language*, 2016, p.196.
6. Sadik A. Digital storytelling, *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 2008, pp.487-506.
7. Mason G.S., Shuman T.R., and Cook K.E. Comparing the effectiveness of an inverted classroom to a traditional classroom in an upper-division engineering course, *IEEE transaction on Education*, 2013, pp. 430-435.